

REGIONAL VARIATIONS IN GENDER DISPARITY IN LITERACY IN HARYANA

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Cite This Article: Rajiv Sindhu, "Regional Variations in Gender Disparity in Literacy in Haryana", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 155-162, 2018.

Abstract:

Gender disparity is one of the most crucial discrimination in many societies. Females always had lower status than males, but the extent of the gap between the sexes varies across cultures and time. The present study is based on secondary data. In the present paper an attempt has been made to study the regional variations in literacy rate in the state of Haryana. It is also aimed at examining the gender disparity in literacy in urban and rural Haryana. In the present paper Sopher's disparity index, modified by Kundu and Rao has been employed to compute disparity level in literacy. The study reveals that there is a significant gender disparity manifested in terms of literacy in the state. It is also evident that there is a wide gap in the literacy level of urban and rural areas, males and females and urban and rural females in the state. The study also brings out that the biasness against female is lower in urban areas than the rural areas in the state as the disparity index is low in urban areas across the state.

Key Words: Gender Disparity, Discrimination, Secondary Data, Haryana, Literacy Rate, Disparity Index & Urban and Rural

Introduction:

Literacy is the basic building block and a crucial element in the development of education in society. In the context of Indian society, which is essentially patriarchal, it is women and girls who suffer because of low accessibility to education. In other words, gender becomes an important factor in determining the education level of an individual (India Human Development Report, 2011). Haryana is one of the agriculturally developed states of India. But the state of Haryana has fared poorly in terms of social development. This is reflected in the discrimination met to the women by the society in terms of availing education, health, sanitation, employment and economic self-sufficiency. There is a significant gender disparity manifested in terms of literacy and attainment of education. Though, Haryana is a very small state, the gender disparity in literacy in the state has a significant geographical manifestation. This paper presents the geographical variations in gender disparity in literacy in Haryana.

Area of Study:

Extending over an area of about 44,212 square Km from 27°39' N to 30°55'5" N latitudes and 74°27'8" E to 77°36'5" E longitudes, the study area is the state of Haryana (Fig1). It is situated in the northwestern part of the Indian Union. It is bordered in the northeast by the Siwalik hills and in the east by the Yamuna river. The dry semi-arid region in the southwest and the west is penetrated by the Aravalli ranges, which find extension in parts of Gurugram, Mahendragarh, Rewari, Bhiwani and Jhajjar districts. In the north, the seasonal Ghaggar river forms parts of the boundary between Punjab and Haryana. Starting originally with one division and seven districts, the state today is divided into four divisions and twenty two districts.

Objectives of the Study:

- The present study is aimed at realising the following objectives.
- ✓ To study the regional variations in literacy rate in the state of Haryana.
- ✓ To examine the gender disparity in literacy in urban and rural Haryana.

Method and Material:

The present study is based on secondary data. The data pertaining to district level literacy has been collected from Census of India, 2011. The literacy rates have been computed by dividing the number of literates by respective population minus 0-6 age group population.

Sopher's Disparity Index (1980), modified by Kundu and Rao (1985) has been employed to compute disparity level in literacy.

$$Ds = \log (x_2/x_1) + \log (200 - x_1/200 - x_2)$$

Where, Ds is gender disparity index, x_1 is percentage of literate females to total female population and x_2 is percentage of literate males to total male population. Here, the values of Disparity Index (ranges between 0.00 and 1.00) exhibit a positive correlation with gender gap in literacy, greater the value of Disparity Index higher the rate of disparity between male and female literacy rate. If there is no disparity then the value of Disparity Index would be zero.

Regional Variations in Literacy Rate:

The level of literacy is undoubtedly one of the most important indicators of social and cultural development among the rural society. In fact, it is the necessary first step towards the attainment of education and of higher goal in an individual's life. There are as many 21 states in the country which have literacy rate

higher than the state of Haryana. Table 1 shows the total, male and female literacy rates and gender disparity index for total, urban and rural population in Haryana in 2011. It is evident that there is a wide gap in the literacy level of urban and rural areas (12 percentage points), males and females (18 percentage points) and urban and rural females (17 percentage points) in the state.

FIG 1

Table 1: Haryana: Literacy Rate and Gender Disparity in Literacy: 2011

Districts	Literacy Rate (Total) (Per Cent)			Disparity Index	Literacy Rate (Rural) (Per Cent)		
	Male	Female	Total		Male	Female	Total
1. Panchkula	87.04	75.99	81.88	0.10	82.66	67.50	75.64
2. Ambala	87.34	75.50	81.75	0.11	84.17	69.36	77.13
3. Yamunanagar	83.84	71.38	77.99	0.11	80.81	65.92	73.80
4. Kurukshetra	83.02	68.84	76.31	0.13	80.85	64.61	73.11
5. Kaithal	77.98	59.24	69.15	0.18	76.02	56.14	66.67
6. Karnal	81.82	66.82	74.73	0.14	79.50	62.28	71.37
7. Panipat	83.71	67.00	75.94	0.15	81.82	61.74	72.50
8. Sonipat	87.18	69.80	79.12	0.16	85.97	66.39	76.93
9. Jind	80.81	60.76	71.44	0.19	78.89	57.34	68.85
10. Fatehabad	76.14	58.87	67.92	0.17	74.50	55.65	65.52
11. Sirsa	76.43	60.40	68.82	0.16	73.82	56.10	65.41
12. Hisar	82.20	62.25	72.89	0.19	79.40	56.64	68.74
13. Bhiwani	85.65	63.54	75.21	0.21	84.99	61.00	73.67
14. Rohtak	87.65	71.72	80.22	0.14	86.01	66.08	76.81
15. Jhajjar	89.31	70.73	80.65	0.17	88.94	68.46	79.39
16. Mahendragarh	89.72	64.57	77.72	0.23	89.56	63.00	76.88
17. Rewari	91.44	69.57	80.99	0.20	91.41	67.03	79.69
18. Gurugram	90.46	77.98	84.70	0.11	89.86	69.11	80.08
19. Nuh	69.94	36.60	54.08	0.38	68.56	33.71	51.99
20. Faridabad	88.61	73.84	81.70	0.13	84.66	60.13	73.18
21. Palwal	82.66	54.23	69.32	0.28	81.59	49.85	66.72
State	84.06	65.94	75.55	0.17	81.55	60.02	71.42

Districts	Disparity Index	Literacy Rate (Rural) (Per Cent)			Disparity Index
		Male	Female	Total	
1. Panchkula	0.14	90.47	82.48	86.72	0.07
2. Ambala	0.14	91.21	83.20	87.46	0.07
3. Yamunanagar	0.14	88.47	79.86	84.45	0.08
4. Kurukshetra	0.15	88.13	79.26	84.01	0.08
5. Kaithal	0.20	84.87	70.08	77.88	0.14
6. Karnal	0.16	87.10	77.07	82.35	0.09
7. Panipat	0.19	85.89	73.07	79.93	0.12
8. Sonipat	0.18	89.86	77.13	83.90	0.11
9. Jind	0.21	87.25	72.07	80.11	0.14
10. Fatehabad	0.19	83.03	72.39	77.97	0.10
11. Sirsa	0.18	84.36	73.42	79.17	0.10
12. Hisar	0.22	88.09	74.30	81.71	0.12
13. Bhiwani	0.23	88.34	73.82	81.48	0.13
14. Rohtak	0.18	89.95	79.20	84.87	0.10
15. Jhajjar	0.19	90.41	77.41	84.34	0.12
16. Mahendragarh	0.25	90.65	73.94	82.71	0.15
17. Rewari	0.22	91.54	77.03	84.73	0.13
18. Gurugram	0.19	90.73	82.06	86.76	0.08
19. Nuh	0.41	80.09	57.71	69.42	0.22
20. Faridabad	0.23	89.59	77.25	83.82	0.11
21. Palwal	0.32	86.16	68.45	77.81	0.16
State	0.21	88.63	76.9	83.14	0.11

FIG 2

FIG 3

FIG 4

Figure 2 shows that there are perceptible regional variations in literacy level of total population. 75.55 per cent of total population is literate in the state. The gap in the literacy rate between the most (Gurugram) and least (Nuh) literate districts is 31 percentage points. Panchkula and Ambala in north and Gurugram, Faridabad, Rohtak, Jhajjar and Rewari are the districts where more than 80 per cent of total population is literate. On the other hand, Kaithal, Fatehabad, Sirsa, Palwal and Nuh are the districts having less than 70 per cent total literate population. It is evident from Figure 1 that male literacy is as high as 84.06 per cent with regional variations. Rewari and Gurugram are the districts having more than 90 per cent male literacy rate while Kaithal, Fatehabad, Sirsa and Nuh districts recorded less than 80 per cent male literacy rate. Only 65.94 per cent females are literate in the state with considerable regional variations. In the district of Nuh only 36.60 per cent of females are literate. Panchkula, Ambala and Gurugram are the only districts having more than 75 per cent female literacy rate.

Figure 3 depicts that 83.14 per cent population is literate in the urban areas of Haryana. However the gap in urban literacy rate between the most (Gurugram) and least (Nuh) literate districts is about 18 percentage points. The regional variations in male literacy rate are very low in urban areas where 88.63 per cent of males are literate. In urban areas of Panchkula, Ambala and Gurugram districts more than 80 per cent females are literate. On the other hand in Palwal and Nuh districts less than 70 per cent urban females are literate. Figure 4 presents significant regional variations in literacy level of rural population. 71.42 per cent of rural total population is literate in the state. The gap in the rural literacy rate between the most (Gurugram) and least (Nuh) literate districts is 28 percentage points. 81.55 percent of rural male population is literate in the state, Rural male literacy rate is highest in Rewari district (91.41 per cent) and lowest in Nuh (68.56 per cent) district. The state records only 60.02 per cent female literacy rate in rural areas. Highest rural female literacy rate is noted in Ambala followed by Gurugram district while it is lowest in Nuh (33.71 per cent) followed by Palwal district.

FIG 5

Regional Variations in Gender Disparity in Literacy:

Gender disparity in literacy has been shown in Figure No. 5 for urban, rural and total population in Haryana in 2011. There is a significant gender disparity in literacy in rural areas (0.21) as compared to urban areas of the state (0.11). In the urban areas, highest gender disparity is recorded in Nuh district being disparity index 0.22. In other districts disparity index is less than 0.20, infact northern districts of the state including Panchkula, Ambala, Yamunanagar, Kurukshetra and Karnal and district of Gurugram noted disparity index less than 0.10. On the other hand, in the rural areas, highest gender disparity in literacy is also found in Nuh district but disparity index is as high as 0.41. Palwal is another district where disparity index is more than 0.30. In other districts disparity index ranges between 0.14 and 0.25.

Conclusion:

Despite being a small state, Haryana represents large regional variations in literacy rate. It is also observed that the biasness against female is lower in urban areas than the rural areas in the state as the disparity index is low in urban areas across the state.

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